

→ https://www.earthscope-program-2003-2018.org/articles/SN_hot_went_mantle_NMSZ.html¹

MESS 0021

GEO 2.22: New Madrid Zone and Blue Ridge Mountain Chain - Magmaflux

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October 2022

ABSTRACT

Previous work was performed in observation of gravitic and magnetic anomalies, in order to look for electrogeological evidence, and for incidence of electrometeorological events, particularly tornadoes. The question of other considerations was raised in 'peer review' (on the Pulse), such as magma, water, wind, and heat data. In this work, there are some mineralogical (historical, high definition) maps and some discussion of historical and other EPEMC considerations, and various suggestions for future work.

Keywords: New Madrid - Smokies - Blue Ridge - magma - faults

¹ Figure 1 - Magmaflux below the New Madrid [Seismic] Zone; credit: Langston et al.

Figure 2 - 1932 highly detailed geological map of the USA; credit: USGS/Stose & Ljungstedt²

² <https://i.redd.it/89g6rx8939t51.jpg> (6000px HD; click link or image to enlarge)

Appalachia, Blue Ridge & the Great Smokey Mountains NP → Shenandoah NP

Figure 3 - zoom in on the map; including the Pine Mountain flux CSK, and the Knobs Lichtenburg, etc.

Note the Smokies' uplift, and if it is a cathode then the region identified in MESS 0020³ is dwarfed by far.

Looking at the keys in the following pages, we definitely see volcanism involved in the mineralism, and apparently at Shenandoah NP!

³ MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux

Figures 4-7: keys from zoom in. (click the ones on the right to expand them)

Map Identifications

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|--|---|---|
| <p>A. Anode? Seat of the Allegewi/Adena-Hopewell</p> <p>B. Another anode? Note Old Stone Fort at Orange arrow (Nicotani or older⁴?)</p> <p>C. Super-Cathode? Great Smokey Mountains NP and Rainforest</p> <p>D. Gravity and Magnetic anomalies, green arrow at Shenandoah (see Fig. 8)</p> <p>E. Pine Mountain flux CSK</p> <p>F. New Madrid Zone series of faults; note the Garden of the Gods at the yellow arrow, and see MESS 0019⁵ for earthquake data</p> <p>G. Jellico Bend Cathode, with magnetic accumulation</p> | <p>H. Breaks Interstate anode</p> <p>I. Big South Fork gravity escarpment</p> <p>J. Red River Gorge sinusoidal peak</p> <p>K. Bluegrass Ordovician dome, seat of the Nicotani/Padoucan power and reach of the KY Coffee Tree</p> <p>L. Big Sink Perattian Thunderbolt</p> <p>M. Jephtha Knob astrobleme</p> <p>N. Spratt Site/Squatter Man 'serpent' mound, extent of Ft. Ancient power, and of KY Coffee Tree</p> <p>O. Portsmouth Earthworks</p> <p>P. O'Byam's Fort/edge of Nicotani power</p> | <p>Q. Land between the Lakes</p> <p>R. Big Bone Lick - site of megafauna extinctions described as by Thunderbolt, by Delaware to T. Jefferson</p> <p>S. Devil's Backbone upper/western fort of Nicotani</p> <p>T. Middlesboro Crater & Cumberland Gap - the Warrior's Road</p> <p>U. Knobs Region Lichtenburg Formation (uplift)</p> <p>V. Fort Knox Dome & tioga Falls</p> <p>W. Great Serpent Mound crypt-explosive site and Comet Venus Effigy</p> |
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Figure 8 (Above) - USGS map

⁴ The site is too large for Nicotani and too close to Chilokee so if aged like Poverty Point: it is a vanished empire.

⁵ MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornado New Madrid Zone & magnetics

The Importance of EPEMC's Approach to geological and mythic and historic records

Looking at Figure 8, we see that there really is no way to discuss history, particularly hidden or repressed history, without a continuing discussion on geography and geology. The history of the Khumry, of the Alleghewi, the Ameroindians, Cherokee, Mississippians, and the Chinese delegation of Zheng He are all wrapped up in the Ohio River Valley, and that of Kithiki (Kentucky). The caves of Kentucky and the karst regions, also the regions that overlap (fluvial or not) the Knobs' lichtenburgs are central to these groups. But, perhaps more interestingly, it was central to the archaic indians, who were producing perhaps the world's first Dark Earths at the shell middens of the Green (and Tennessee) River. It is also key that the mounds to the north and east are conical (Saturnian), and longburrow (or grave related), and that the mounds to the south and west are platform pyramidal (Jovian). In fact, some of the sites are two stepped platform mounds, and there is one that is a hexagonal cone. But the shell middens are large, flat dark Earth mounds, which are large and ancient. Most of them are over 3,000 years, and some are 7,000 years old, with their peaks being in the Poverty Point aging around 3,500 YBP. Also, there is some utility in knowing the geography of the region in terms of mineral, nutritional value, etc., as it affects human geography or anthropology. And when one understands this, or portions of it, there are myths and recollections of the natives - particularly the story the Delaware chief told to Thomas Jefferson - that make a major difference in considering electrogeology. The Cherokee maintain that Stone Mount in Georgia was raised by thunderbolt. Now, since a) we have a Perattian thunderbolt site that is confirmation of the predictive power of PEMC --> EPEMC, and b) we have discussion of the "power of the Lord" in the Psalms, Exodus, etc., then c) we have reason to suspect the native testimony is not only accurate but undervalued.

For example, we see examples of curled/folding mountains in Arkansas, New Mexico (next to the Three Rivers Petroglyphs), Wudang Mountains (which have numerous electrical connections), and not least of all: the Black Hills of Wyoming. These are suspected to be cathode areas of raised formation (by electric field and arc together).

If this is possible, then consider the anode side, with sudden raised formations (including columnar formations), like Devil's Tower, Ayers Rock, Stone Mountain, Pilot Knob (several), Shiprock, and others. There's another thing that comes to mind, is that the obviousness of the Knobs and Grand Canyon as lichtenburgs underscores that there is some type of difference we are not clear upon. One is raised, the other excavated, both seem to be a direct arch EDM. But then when you compare this with the Pine Mountain complex, we see a completely different result... and then there's the electro-bolides, comets, asteroids, etc.

Is it really so likely that the Jephtha Knob meteorite was formed by striking "coincidentally" at the edge of the Ordovician dome of the Bluegrass? Or that the Hicks' Dome electro-bolide was right along the arc of the Land Between the Lakes? ... right next to and within the New Madrid Zone? That surely strains credulity.

And the fact that there is a massive mine (world's largest) of fluorspar there, in the Kentuckiana, and this may have been key for the Nicotani empire... and that this is all in the same region that the world's largest caves and largest karst region is, and proximal to the world's 2nd oldest riverbed... goes beyond straining credulity. It points to pure relationship, and not coincidence; to causation and not correlation.

Figure 9 - Western Kentucky Fluorspar District; credit: uky.edu⁶

⁶ https://www.uky.edu/KGS/minerals/im_fluorspardistrict.php

Figure 10 - Arc-path of the LBL and Hick's Dome, with Fluorspar District in pathway; credit: Google/author

Electro-bolides

There are, at present, several different grades of EB (comet or asteroid) evidence, and growing:

- ❖ A+ Explosion caught on cameras (multiple) of air burst, with sudden brightening, over Russia. Explosion inordinately powerful and inexplicable just before landing... which is common with bolides entering the atmosphere, but in this case many questions arise. The power is simply out of order with the size of the rock.
- ❖ A 1491 Melbourne comet; Simultaneous Korean astronomer (written) and Australian aboriginal testimony (oral myth), with present chevrons from mega-tsunami *and* nuclear glass, with instant petrification on the beach north of the strike site.
- ❖ A- Comet Shoemaker-Levy 9; explosions recorded from distance in Jupiter. Sizes unusual for kinetic explanation of the event. Rocks the size of Manhattan made scars on Jupiter the size of Earth for extended periods of time.
- ❖ B+ Cumberland Gap "Crooked Smile Keystone"; has the bowshock and yet is part of a clearly larger electric event. Could be two separate events, coincidentally attracted to the same area.
- ❖ B- Hick's Dome (Figure 10); the arc of impact, bow shown facing clearly along the arc, with transmuted fluorspar deposits, and magnetic (not gravitic) anomaly.
- ❖ C Sodom/Gomorrah comet recorded in Sumerian tablet, with vector matching strike in an Italian Alps mountain peak. Multiple cities burned up in the arc blast wave indicate a large bolus
- ❖ D+ 330 or 630AD comet over Wales; said to have burned up Glamorgan and led to the plagues.

Figure 11 (above) - Zoom in for Arkansas area map, with focus on Magnetic Escarpment, accumulation area, and New Madrid Zone; click to expand

NOTE: a distinct lack of Lava Flows.

Figure 12 (below) - Key for Arkansas and Midwest geological region

Figure 13 - "Columnar jointing in the greenstones of Shenandoah National Park, Virginia." Credit: A. Kim"⁷

Figure 14 (below) - Regions of the Taconic volcanics in the Piedmont; credit: PRI

Figure 15 - "Locations of granite intrusions related to the Taconic Orogeny in the Blue Ridge and Piedmont regions of the southeastern United States."; credit: PRI

⁷ <https://earthathome.org/ho/se/rocks-brp/>

Conclusions & Recommendations

The Blue Ridge and Smokies do not appear to the author to have very strong evidence of magma activity to associate with the gravity and magnetic anomalies, as is claimed by the mainstream. There are signs of volcanism, historically, but the explanation that this provides is not very satisfactory regarding the issues raised in MESS0018 re: bipolar fields below the BR chain and the magnetic escarpment forming a negative bubble inside the BR chain, crossing the divide.

Regarding the NMSZ, the author thinks it is clear that there is moving magma, and this might have an association with the magnetic accumulation, and furthermore the author thinks it is related to the tornado production. The increase in solar proton density by 14x had some type of major effect upon the area. People often suggest that they saw changes in sky color well ahead of the arrival of tornadoes, earlier in the day. Perhaps these magma chambers are caused by, or pull down/attract charge/electrical power. The author recommends a 10 year study in the area, with seismicity only as a side study, but the main purpose to be electromagnetic, LiDAR, and other evidence. The hope is to find multi-point signs of evidence from sonar detection to heat and sound conduction to take a look at the causes of either earthquakes, or more interestingly: attractions of vortical weather systems. In the case of the NMSZ, long track tornadoes. In the case of North-Carolina & Virginia, hurricanes.

The author also recommends that readers make no final judgments until mineral and groundwater discussions happen in the next MESSies in the MET & GEO series. But they should at the very least, question all linear or simplistic explanations put forward from the mainstream based upon the work thus far in the series.

References

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